

Mechanism of Ruthenium Tetroxide catalysed Oxidation of Cycloheptanol by Bromate in Alkaline Medium

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Scant attention has been paid to the activity of potassium bromate in the presence of a catalyst in acidic media¹, and no investigation has so far been reported to explain the catalytic role of RuO_4 with potassium bromate as an oxidant in alkaline medium. This prompted us to undertake the present investigation which consists of aqueous alkaline bromate oxidation of cycloheptanol in the presence of RuO_4 as catalyst and mercuric acetate as a Br^- scavenger. Mechanistic aspects are discussed.

Results and Discussion

Spectra of RuO_4 in different concentrations of NaOH were taken on UV Model Beckmann 26 UV spectrophotometer. It was observed that above $1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ NaOH concentration, peaks for both Ru^{VIII} and Ru^{VI} exist and below it, peak for only Ru^{VIII} is obtained. Hence all kinetic observations were taken in the alkali concentration range of $0.30 \times 10^{-3} - 1.30 \times 10^{-3} M$ in order to facilitate Ru^{VIII} catalysis in the oxidation of cycloheptanol by KBrO_3 .

The oxidation of cycloheptanol (Cyhep) by alkaline bromate in presence of RuO_4 yielded the corresponding ketone which was confirmed by tlc and also through the dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNP) derivative.

The values of first order constant k_1 i.e. $(-dc/dt)/[\text{KBrO}_3]$ (*indicating the concentration of KBrO_3 at which $-dc/dt$ was determined) calculated from the plots of unconsumed bromate vs time were constant at all initial concentrations of bromate, indicating the first order dependence on [oxidant] (Table 1). A plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{Cyhep}]$ (Fig. 1A) gave a straight line with slope equal to 1.00 which confirms first order kinetics with respect to cycloheptanol. Variation in concentration of hydroxyl ions

Fig. 1. (A): Plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{Cyhep}]$ at 35° ; $[\text{KBrO}_3]=1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{NaOH}]=3.33 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $[\text{RuO}_4]=13.2 \times 10^{-6} M$. (B) 35° and (C) 45° : Plots of k_1 vs $[\text{RuO}_4]$; $[\text{KBrO}_3]=1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{NaOH}]=3.33 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $[\text{Cyhep}]=1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$.

did not influence the value of k_1 appreciably, showing zero order dependence on $[\text{OH}^-]$ (Table 1).

First order dependence on $[\text{RuO}_4]$ is evident from the close resemblance between the slope value (4.23 and $8.33 \times 10^{-3} M^{-1} s^{-1}$ at 35° and 45° respectively) of k_1 vs $[\text{RuO}_4]$ plot (Fig. 1B, C) and average value of second order rate constants k_2 or $k_1/[\text{RuO}_4]$ (4.10 and $8.16 \times 10^{-3} M^{-1} s^{-1}$ at 35° and 45° respectively).

Negligible effect of variation of ionic strength of the medium and addition of mercuric acetate on reaction rate was observed. The function of mercuric acetate is to eliminate the parallel oxidation by bromine which would have been formed as a result of interaction between Br^- and bromate ion².

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF $[\text{KBrO}_3]$ AND $[\text{NaOH}]$ ON REACTION RATE

$[\text{Cycloheptanol}]=1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{RuO}_4]=13.2 \times 10^{-6} M$, $[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2]=4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$

$[\text{KBrO}_3]$ $\times 10^3 M$	$k_1 (\times 10^4 s^{-1})$ $[\text{NaOH}]=3.33 \times 10^{-4} M$		$[\text{NaOH}]$ $\times 10^4 M$	$k_1 (\times 10^4 s^{-1})$ $[\text{KBrO}_3]=1.00 \times 10^3 M$	
	35°	45°		35°	45°
0.80	4.86	9.78	3.33	5.10	10.22
1.00	5.10	10.22	5.00	5.07	10.02
1.25	5.00	9.82	6.66	4.98	10.08
1.67	4.98	9.90	10.00	5.02	9.98
2.50	5.02	10.10	13.22	5.10	10.40
3.33	4.96	10.12	20.00	4.94	10.02

Thermodynamic parameters were computed from linear Arrhenius plot in the temperature range 30–50°: $\Delta S^\ddagger = 93.61 \pm 0.5 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $\Delta E = 31.9 \pm 0.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

The reactive species of potassium bromate in both acidic and alkaline media is BrO_3^- . In aqueous solution RuO_4 exists in the following equilibria³,

On assuming RuO_4 as reactive species, the rate law requires positive effect of $[\text{OH}^-]$ contrary to its observed negligible effect. Hence RuO_4 as such will not be involved in the catalytic process and HRuO_5^- can safely be assumed to be the reactive species of ruthenium tetroxide.

Now on the basis of the above discussion and other kinetic observations the following steps are suggested as reaction route,

The complex C_1 may be assigned the following structure,

The rate law proposed on the basis of steps (i–iii) has been expressed as equation (1),

$$\frac{-d[\text{BrO}_3^-]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{RuO}_4] [\text{S}] [\text{BrO}_3^-] [\text{OH}^-]}{k_{-2} [\text{OH}^-] + k_3 [\text{BrO}_3^-]} \quad (1)$$

where $K_1 = k_1/k_{-1}$.

Since step (iii) is slow, hence k_3 is small and $k_{-2} [\text{OH}^-] \gg k_3 [\text{BrO}_3^-]$. Therefore equation (1) is reduced to equation (2),

$$\frac{-d[\text{BrO}_3^-]}{dt} = K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{RuO}_4] [\text{S}] [\text{BrO}_3^-] \quad (2)$$

The rate law (equation 2) accords fully well with the observed kinetic results.

Experimental

Aqueous solutions of all the chemicals (AnalaR) were prepared in triple-distilled water. Ruthenium tetroxide (Sigma) was prepared in sodium hydroxide of known strength. The development of the reaction was noted by examining aliquots of the reaction mixture for unconsumed KBrO_3 iodometrically using starch indicator, after suitable time intervals upto completion of about 75% of the reaction.

References

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